

Abstract

This article discusses the size and composition of Canadian mining-related GDP, then compares them with the mine plan for a proposed new mega mine. The article introduces methods for estimating the direct and indirect impacts on GDP from new mineral revenue from the new mega mine. It shows how to compare the planned mine revenue with national GDP levels using several methods that are more or less apples-to-apples comparisons. The article finds that a single project can have a massive impact on national statistics. For example, it estimates that the total combined direct and indirect GDP impacts from the project are larger than the forecast value for the entire GDP from copper mining in some years.

Keywords: GDP, Mining, Canada, Simulation

JEL Codes:

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Q33 - Resource Booms
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GDP from Mining in Canada and A New Mega Project

This article discusses the size and composition of Canadian mining-related GDP, then compares them with the mine plan for a proposed new mega mine. The article introduces methods for estimating the direct and indirect impacts on GDP from new mineral revenue from the new mega mine. It shows how to compare the planned mine revenue with national GDP levels using several methods that are more or less apples-to-apples comparisons. The article finds that a single project can have a massive impact on national statistics. For example, it estimates that the total combined direct and indirect GDP impacts from the project are larger than the forecast value for the entire GDP from copper mining in some years.

1. Data Definitions

The initial data set covers the years 2006-2012. The data are from Statistics Canada (2012), “Gross domestic product (GDP) at basic prices, by industry, annual average, industry detail (x 1,000,000)” (Table 36-10-0434-06), which shows how mining's contribution to GDP compares with other macroeconomic statistics.

Table 1.1: Canadian National GDP Macroeconomics 2006-2012

	All Industries T001	Mining, oil, and gas extraction [21]	Support for mining, oil and gas	Oil and Gas extraction [211]	Mining [212]
2012	\$1,287,773,500,000	\$56,950,000,000	\$7,678,500,000	\$41,863,500,000	\$8,200,000,000
2011	\$1,266,590,000,000	\$57,422,000,000	\$8,621,000,000	\$41,427,000,000	\$8,596,000,000
2010	\$1,233,930,000,000	\$54,967,000,000	\$7,479,000,000	\$40,113,000,000	\$8,170,000,000
2009	\$1,193,211,000,000	\$52,125,000,000	\$5,419,000,000	\$39,693,000,000	\$6,932,000,000
2008	\$1,229,786,000,000	\$56,538,000,000	\$7,624,000,000	\$40,748,000,000	\$8,967,000,000
2007	\$1,218,981,000,000	\$57,776,000,000	\$7,159,000,000	\$42,448,000,000	\$8,777,000,000
2006	\$1,191,403,000,000	\$57,271,000,000	\$7,937,000,000	\$41,571,000,000	\$8,674,000,000

The following tables show these NAICS mining categories relative to all industrial GDP and to the GDP of two bulk mining NAICS categories. The metals ore mining segment is \$3 to \$4 billion, with roughly half that in copper, nickel, lead, and zinc.

Table 1.2: Natural Resources as Percent of Total Industrial GDP, 2006-2012

% Of All Industries			
Mining, oil, and gas extraction [21]	Oil and Gas extraction [211]	Support for mining, oil and gas	Mining [212]
4.6%	3.3%	0.6%	0.7%

Table 1.3: Bulk Mining, 2006-2012

	Coal mining [2121]	Potash mining
2012	\$871,000,000	\$1,174,000,000
2011	\$913,000,000	\$1,314,500,000
2010	\$921,000,000	\$1,440,000,000
2009	\$777,000,000	\$1,267,000,000
2008	\$881,000,000	\$587,000,000
2007	\$827,000,000	\$1,399,000,000
2006	\$859,000,000	\$1,534,000,000

Table 1.4: Mining for Metals and More, 2006-2012

	Metals ore mining [2122]	Gold and silver [21222]	Iron ore mining [21221]	Diamond mining	Copper, nickel, Pb Zn [21223]
2012	\$3,520,000,000	\$668,000,000	\$520,000,000	\$1,058,000,000	\$1,998,000,000
2011	\$3,607,000,000	\$664,000,000	\$520,000,000	\$1,139,000,000	\$2,100,000,000
2010	\$3,372,000,000	\$674,000,000	\$580,000,000	\$1,284,000,000	\$1,780,000,000
2009	\$3,169,000,000	\$671,000,000	\$482,000,000	\$1,237,000,000	\$1,675,000,000
2008	\$3,854,000,000	\$644,000,000	\$558,000,000	\$1,523,000,000	\$2,343,000,000
2007	\$3,707,000,000	\$656,000,000	\$561,000,000	\$1,702,000,000	\$2,188,000,000
2006	\$3,808,000,000	\$729,000,000	\$612,000,000	\$1,306,000,000	\$2,165,000,000

The final segment is about other types of mining.

Table 1.5: Other Types of Mining, 2006-2012

	Quarry & Non-metallic mining [2123]	Other non-metallic mining	Stone mining [2123]	Salt mining	Other Local Mining
2012	\$3,802,000,000	\$2,742,500,000	\$580,500,000	\$203,000,000	\$7,328,000,000
2011	\$4,318,000,000	\$3,016,000,000	\$603,000,000	\$267,000,000	\$8,204,000,000
2010	\$4,082,000,000	\$2,814,000,000	\$619,000,000	\$225,000,000	\$7,740,000,000
2009	\$2,926,000,000	\$1,786,000,000	\$607,000,000	\$300,000,000	\$5,619,000,000
2008	\$4,507,000,000	\$3,196,000,000	\$591,000,000	\$298,000,000	\$8,592,000,000
2007	\$4,662,000,000	\$3,438,000,000	\$562,000,000	\$228,000,000	\$8,890,000,000
2006	\$4,042,000,000	\$2,718,000,000	\$559,000,000	\$267,000,000	\$7,586,000,000

The article repeats these tables for another time period, from 2020 to 2024. There is some missing data in the earlier time period compared to the whole dataset, so I estimate several figures using the methods as described below. For 2020-2024, the Mining [212] is estimated as total bulk mining, total metals mining, and other local mining. Also, the data is reported in a way that separates oil and gas from oil sands. Also, the 2025 data separates support spending for mining from that for oil and gas. The numbers I calculate are in bold.

Table 1.6: Canadian National GDP Macroeconomics, 2020-2024

	All Industries T001	Mining, oil, and gas extraction [21]	Oil and gas inc. oil sands	Support for all mining, oil and gas	Mining [212]
2020	N/A	\$104,738,000,000	\$64,814,000,000	\$10,349,000,000	\$39,924,000,000
2021	N/A	\$108,213,000,000	\$67,932,000,000	\$12,162,000,000	\$40,281,000,000
2022	N/A	\$110,635,000,000	\$70,018,000,000	\$14,778,000,000	\$40,617,000,000
2023	N/A	\$112,632,000,000	\$71,167,000,000	\$14,857,000,000	\$41,465,000,000
2024	N/A	\$117,349,000,000	\$73,904,000,000	\$15,418,000,000	\$43,445,000,000

Table 1.7: Natural Resources as Percent of Total Industrial GDP, 2020-2024

	Coal mining [2121]	Potash mining	Total Bulk Mining
2020	\$2,569,000,000	\$3,814,000,000	\$6,383,000,000
2021	\$2,768,000,000	\$3,908,000,000	\$6,676,000,000
2022	\$2,568,000,000	\$3,935,000,000	\$6,503,000,000
2023	\$2,870,000,000	\$3,799,000,000	\$6,669,000,000
2024	\$2,682,000,000	\$4,115,000,000	\$6,797,000,000

Table 1.8: Mining for Metals and More, 2020-2024

	Metals ore mining [2122]	Gold and silver ore mining [21222]	Iron ore mining [21221]	Diamond mining	Copper, nickel, lead and zinc ore mining [21223]	Other metal ore mining [21229]	Total Metals Mining
2020	\$14,758,000,000	\$4,827,000,000	\$3,659,000,000	N/A	\$5,702,000,000	\$570,000,000	\$29,516,000,000
2021	\$14,673,000,000	\$5,611,000,000	\$3,600,000,000	N/A	\$4,785,000,000	\$677,000,000	\$29,346,000,000
2022	\$14,743,000,000	\$5,659,000,000	\$3,947,000,000	N/A	\$4,420,000,000	\$717,000,000	\$29,486,000,000
2023	\$15,157,000,000	\$5,663,000,000	\$3,820,000,000	N/A	\$4,596,000,000	\$1,078,000,000	\$30,314,000,000
2024	\$16,209,000,000	\$6,031,000,000	\$3,972,000,000	N/A	\$4,850,000,000	\$1,356,000,000	\$32,418,000,000

Table 1.9: Other Types of Mining, 2020-2024

	Sand, gravel, clay, and ceramic and refractory minerals mining and quarrying [21232]	Other non-metallic mineral mining and quarrying (except potash) [21239X]5	Stone mining and quarrying [21231]	Salt mining	Other Local Mining
2020	\$1,077,000,000	\$1,809,000,000	\$1,139,000,000	N/A	\$4,025,000,000
2021	\$1,161,000,000	\$1,847,000,000	\$1,251,000,000	N/A	\$4,259,000,000
2022	\$1,372,000,000	\$1,930,000,000	\$1,326,000,000	N/A	\$4,628,000,000
2023	\$1,390,000,000	\$1,719,000,000	\$1,373,000,000	N/A	\$4,482,000,000
2024	\$1,453,000,000	\$1,351,000,000	\$1,426,000,000	N/A	\$4,230,000,000

There are several minor differences in the data over time. For example, there is no information on diamond and salt mining in Statistics Canada (2025) data.

The following tables compare the average levels for key variables between the two eras.

Table 1.10: Comparing Annual GDP Statistics for Canada, 2006-2012 versus 2020-2024

	Mining, oil, and gas extraction [21]	Oil and gas inc. oil sands	Support for all mining, oil and gas	Mining [212]
2020-2024	\$110,713,400,000	\$69,567,000,000	\$13,512,800,000	\$41,146,400,000
2006-2012	\$56,149,857,143	\$7,416,785,714	\$41,123,357,143	\$8,330,857,143
Total Growth	97%	838%	-67%	394%

Table 1.11: Comparing Annual GDP from Bulk Mining, 2006-2012 versus 2020-2024

	Coal mining [2121]	Potash mining	Total Bulk Mining
2020-2024	\$2,691,400,000	\$3,914,200,000	\$6,605,600,000
2006-2012	\$864,142,857	\$1,245,071,429	\$2,109,214,286
Total Growth	211%	214%	213%

Table 1.12: Comparing GDP from Mining for Metals and More, 2006-2012 versus 2020-2024

	Metals ore mining [2122]	Gold and silver ore mining [21222]	Iron ore mining [21221]	Diamond mining	Copper, nickel, lead and zinc ore mining [21223]
2020-2024	\$15,108,000,000	\$5,558,200,000	\$3,799,600,000	N/A	\$4,870,600,000
2006-2012	\$3,576,714,286	\$672,285,714	\$547,571,429	\$1,321,285,714	\$2,035,571,429
Total Growth	322%	727%	594%	N/A	139%

Table 1.13: Comparing GDP from Other Mining Types, 2006-2012 versus 2020-2024

	Sand, gravel, clay, and ceramic and refractory minerals mining and quarrying [21232]	Other non-metallic mineral mining and quarrying (except potash) [21239X]5	Stone mining and quarrying [21231]	Salt mining	Total "Other Mining"
2020-2024	\$1,290,600,000	\$1,731,200,000	\$1,303,000,000	N/A	\$4,324,800,000
2006-2012	\$4,048,428,571	\$2,815,785,714	\$588,785,714	\$255,428,571	\$7,708,428,571
Total Growth	-68%	-39%	121%	N/A	-44%

There may be some mismatches in data definitions between the two eras, but all data are standardized according to the NAICS definitions. Some aggregated data, like “Mining [212],” were included in the 2006-2012 data but not in the 2025 data. I calculate the total mining GDP as follows: total bulk mining, total metals ore mining, and total other mining.

The results show significant variation across different parts of the mining economy over time. I highlight the 727% increase in the value of gold and silver ore mining [21222], from an average of \$672,285,714 in the first era to \$5,558,200,000 in the second era (2006-2012 and 2020-2024). The total value of metal ore mining [2122] in the second era averages \$15 billion per year, which is an important reference point.

2. Toy Model with New Mega Mine

Seabridge Gold Corp. (2022) presents an economic study for the KSM project, a proposed copper mine in BC. It could be one of the world’s next-generation largest mines, with a +30-year production plan, life-of-mine total revenues greater than USD \$80 billion, and estimated total taxes on profits of USD \$14.7 billion for various levels of government. The KSM porphyry copper deposit is similar to those in the Atacama Desert in Chile. Seabridge Gold Corp. is a company that represents a success story for the domestic mining exploration and development business and for profit-motivated firms.

I calculate the total GDP impact of the KSM project as follows: first, revenue times a multiplier. Second, I add that amount to capital costs. I include capital costs because they are the exogenous funding needed to get the project started. I include revenue because it represents the total new economic activity generated by mining that year. KSM mine revenue represents the gross value of mineral production, comparable to the Natural Resources Canada macroeconomic report, which estimates a multiplier of 1.75-2.4x, as shown below.

Table 2.1: KSM Mine Plan Economic Model and GDP Impact Estimates

	Capital Spending	Revenue	GDP Direct (Capital Costs + 1.75x Revenue)	GDP Total (Capital Costs + 2.4x Revenue)
-5	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$1,072,000,000	\$1,072,000,000
-4	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$1,072,000,000	\$1,072,000,000
-3	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$1,072,000,000	\$1,072,000,000
-2	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$1,072,000,000	\$1,072,000,000
-1	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$1,072,000,000	\$1,072,000,000
0	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$1,072,000,000	\$1,072,000,000
1	\$723,000,000	\$1,998,000,000	\$4,219,500,000	\$5,518,200,000
2	\$300,000,000	\$2,464,000,000	\$4,612,000,000	\$6,213,600,000
3	\$162,000,000	\$4,392,000,000	\$7,848,000,000	\$10,702,800,000
4	\$109,000,000	\$3,775,000,000	\$6,715,250,000	\$9,169,000,000
5	\$68,000,000	\$3,997,000,000	\$7,062,750,000	\$9,660,800,000
6	-\$25,000,000	\$3,251,000,000	\$5,664,250,000	\$7,777,400,000
7	-\$27,000,000	\$2,713,000,000	\$4,720,750,000	\$6,484,200,000
AVERAGE	\$595,538,462	\$3,227,142,857	\$5,834,642,857	\$7,932,285,714

The net present value of the total GDP impact ranges from \$40 billion to \$60 billion over the pre-production and start-of-production periods. Annual GDP impact ranges from \$1 billion to \$10 billion. This equation calculates the total GDP impact equal to KSM mine revenue times a multiplier plus capital costs each year:

$$GDP (KSM) = Revenue * Multiplier + Capital Costs$$

The KSM mine revenue is the same thing as the total value of mineral production, as in Natural Resources (2025), which discusses the total value of mineral production, the direct GDP impact, and the indirect GDP impact. At the national level across Canada, total direct GDP impact (\$112 billion) divided by total mine revenue (\$64 billion) gives a multiplier ratio (1.75x) to represent how much faster the direct GDP increases relative to total mine revenue. Another key ratio is total mining GDP (\$156 billion) divided by mining revenue (\$64 billion), yielding 2.4x in this case. The difference in multipliers is due to the indirect GDP impacts.

Mining revenue may not have a direct impact on GDP because some of it may be recorded as profit, “retained earnings,” or other line items that are not counted towards GDP. The income approach to GDP uses mine revenue to calculate the direct impact on GDP. Instead of revenues, mining costs can also be used to estimate the direct GDP impact of mining activity, as determined by the costing approach designed to avoid double-counting. The income approach does not double-count the GDP impact from mining revenue because it is primary production. The macroeconomic statistics from Natural Resources Canada enable comparisons between mine revenue and the GDP impacts of a particular project.

For KSM, total mine revenue over this timeline is \$22.5 billion (Seabridge Gold Corp., 2022). There is an additional mine life of +30 years, but this calculation focuses on the first 7 years of production and 6 years of pre-production. The direct GDP impact is \$39.5 billion, and the total impact is \$54.2 billion, based on multipliers of 1.75x and 2.4x. These revenue impacts accrue over 7 years, and the incremental total annual GDP impact ranges from \$5 billion to almost \$8 billion after the mine starts production.

For comparison, the average annual GDP from 2020 to 2024 from metal ore mining [2122] is around \$15 billion. The KSM project estimates average annual revenue of \$3.2 billion and total operating costs of \$750 million. The comparable figure here is annual revenue, because that is the value of mineral production, which affects GDP through revenue and capital costs.

The effects of KSM are enormous. If considered gold-only, KSM would account for 20% of the entire gold business over the production window. Moreover, if we consider copper-only, then it becomes +50% the entire copper business in Canada. In some years, KSM's total GDP impact exceeds the entire copper mining GDP forecast.

Table 2.2: Total GDP from KSM, Net Present Value of GDP, and % of Average NAICS Industry

	TOTAL GDP @ KSM (2.4x multiplier on Revenue plus Capital Costs)	NPV of Total GDP KSM	As % of All Metals Ore Mining	As % of Gold Mining	As % of Copper Mining
-5	\$1,072,000,000	\$35,182,424,161	7%	19%	22%
-4	\$1,072,000,000	\$38,112,537,577	6%	16%	21%
-3	\$1,072,000,000	\$41,335,662,335	6%	14%	19%
-2	\$1,072,000,000	\$44,881,099,568	5%	12%	18%
-1	\$1,072,000,000	\$48,781,080,525	5%	10%	17%
0	\$1,072,000,000	\$53,071,059,578	4%	8%	16%
1	\$5,518,200,000	\$57,790,036,536	19%	37%	75%
2	\$6,213,600,000	\$58,534,711,189	19%	35%	79%
3	\$10,702,800,000	\$58,658,453,308	29%	51%	128%
4	\$9,169,000,000	\$54,305,369,639	22%	37%	102%
5	\$9,660,800,000	\$51,050,777,603	21%	33%	101%
6	\$7,827,400,000	\$46,978,926,363	15%	23%	76%
7	\$6,538,200,000	\$44,383,290,000	11%	16%	60%
AVERAGE	\$4,774,000,000	\$48,697,340,645	13%	24%	56%

Chart 1: Total GDP from KSM, Net Present Value of GDP, and % of Average NAICS Industry

GDP Impact from KSM and % of Canadian Mining GDP

In its biggest year, the KSM project contributed \$10 billion to GDP. This is larger than the entire copper mining industry GDP as forecasted here. The forecast is based on the average value for gold mining GDP from 2020 to 2024, then growing at a 7% annual rate, which is the average growth rate for the two eras, 2006-2012 and 2020-2024, as calculated here. The gold industry was estimated to grow at 18% per year, and the entire mining GDP at 12%. These results show that a single project, KSM, could double Canada's copper GDP.

Mining industries may be growing faster than historical factors, so the KSM project may appear smaller. However, the KSM revenues may increase relative to the 2022 economic study and make KSM appear larger. Moreover, KSM also has a total mine life that is four times longer, which continues to impact GDP through long-term revenue and sustaining capital costs. A single project can account for almost 10% of national mining across the entire pre-production and production cycle.

Table 2.3: Total GDP from KSM, Direct Taxes, and Indirect Taxes

	GDP IMPACT (TOTAL)	Direct Taxes	KSM Operating Cash Flow	KSM Effective Tax Rate	Indirect Taxes
-5	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$0	N/A	\$107,200,000
-4	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$0	N/A	\$107,200,000
-3	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$0	N/A	\$107,200,000
-2	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$0	N/A	\$107,200,000
-1	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$0	N/A	\$107,200,000
0	\$1,072,000,000	\$0	\$0	N/A	\$107,200,000
1	\$5,518,200,000	\$28,000,000	\$1,364,000,000	2%	\$551,819,800
2	\$6,213,600,000	\$36,000,000	\$1,742,000,000	2%	\$621,359,754
3	\$10,702,800,000	\$181,000,000	\$3,405,000,000	5%	\$1,070,279,561
4	\$9,169,000,000	\$730,000,000	\$3,018,000,000	24%	\$916,899,623
5	\$9,660,800,000	\$1,002,000,000	\$3,094,000,000	32%	\$966,079,600
6	\$7,827,400,000	\$798,000,000	\$2,385,000,000	33%	\$782,739,675
7	\$6,538,200,000	\$624,000,000	\$1,858,000,000	34%	\$653,819,729
AVERAGE	\$4,774,000,000	\$485,571,429	\$2,409,428,571	19%	\$794,713,963

How much does a mega mine like this pay in taxes? I use the amounts for direct taxes as in the Seabridge Gold Corp (2022) report. I estimate indirect taxes as follows: 10% of indirect GDP after removing revenue. I remove the revenue because taxes are already calculated on revenue in the Seabridge economic study, so I remove it from the total GDP impact, then calculate the effective tax rate on the total GDP impact. I assume the total GDP impact equals capital costs plus 2.4x revenue each year, and the tax rate is 10%.

The results in Table 2.3 show that indirect taxes are actually larger than direct taxes from the KSM project. They are over 60% larger on average per year. Indirect taxes actually start earlier because capital cost spending triggers them from the start of the mine plan, whereas direct taxes only start after the mine is in production. Indirect impacts are an essential factor in understanding the economic impacts of mining.

It is possible to compare KSM mine revenue, direct GDP impact, and indirect GDP impact to reference values for metals mining. The KSM mine plan has an average annual revenue of \$3.2 billion and costs of \$753 million, as in Table 2.1. KSM has an average operating income of \$2.4 billion, as shown in Table 2.3. The national metals ore mining GDP for Canada was \$15 billion from 2020 to 2024 and \$3.5 billion from 2006 to 2012, as in Table 1.12. These amounts provide an apples-to-apples comparison between metals ore mining GDP and KSM mine revenue. The total revenue in the mine plan shows that the KSM project is around 20% the size of the Canadian mining industry for 2020-2024, or 100% for 2006-2012!

The Seabridge Gold project, KSM, is a porphyry copper deposit. These can be massive mineral deposits that can yield generations of mining comparable to the porphyry copper deposits in Chile. For example, an economic study by Seabridge Gold (2022c) estimates capital costs to compare with those of porphyry deposits in Chile. Seabridge Gold's KSM project has total initial capital costs, referred to as "Total Direct Costs," of \$4.2 billion. Total sustaining capital costs \$3.2 billion. These are among the most considerable costs for any proposed project worldwide.

For comparison, Nourali and Osanloo (2019) report capital costs for the 15 most significant porphyry copper projects in Chile, averaging \$2.3 billion and ranging up to \$5.7 billion (all figures are in USD). These are truly gigantic mines. The economic study for KSM (Seabridge Gold, 2022c) estimates total direct capital costs of \$7.5 billion over the life of mine, which is larger than any value in the Chilean dataset. KSM represents one of the most significant new mines in the world. It is owned by a company with no mines in production, as a development company built on exploration success.

How many other projects in Canada are like KSM? What about others that are bigger or smaller? How many economic studies do we have? How many are owned by operating mining companies that do not publish economic studies? What inventory of projects in Canada and what likelihood for each one to go ahead on an immediate timeline? Near-term timeline? Long-term timeline? Mapping out the necessary infrastructure changes required to make each project feasible on each timeline? Costs of infrastructure to unlock clusters of projects? Understanding the different dimensions of data to compare mining projects to estimate the impact of economic development from the mining industry.

The KSM Project has long-term potential. Imagine repeating this first phase of metal production four more times over the life of a mine for a gigantic deposit. The mine plan assumes the processing capacity remains the same to reduce sustaining capital costs. The screenshot from Seabridge Gold Corp. (2022) below shows the chart of annual revenues after the first 7 years of production and 6 years of pre-production, extending to mine closure over almost 40 years. The model assumes that the net cash flow after year 13 is the same.

22.4.3 TAXES AND POST-TAX FINANCIAL RESULTS

At the 2022 Base Case metal prices and exchange rate used for this study, total estimated taxes payable on KSM profits are US\$14.7 billion over the 33-year LOM. The total estimated taxes payable by the mine in all scenarios provided are shown in Table 22.3.

The post-tax undiscounted annual cash flows are illustrated in Figure 22.1.

Figure 22.1 Post-tax Undiscounted Annual and Cumulative Cash Flow

Source: Tetra Tech, 2022

How does the valuation of the project vary over time? I use KSM's long-term cash flow profile to estimate the Net Present Value Profile (Bell, 2017). I assume a 10% discount rate throughout. I use two different assumptions for the time horizons, based on the number of periods included in the NPV calculation, as follows. The NPV is negative when using a 13-year horizon, which includes the first 6 years of pre-production and 7 years of production. However, over 30 years with a 10% NPV, we get a significant positive NPV of \$3.2 billion from the start of the project.

The Net Present Value Profile for the KSM Project is provided below:

Table 2.4: NPV Profile of Operating Income from KSM Mine Plan

	NPV (13 years)	NPV (30 years)
-5	-\$50,610,549	\$3,286,766,099
-4	\$1,374,932,898	\$4,687,442,709
-3	\$2,943,030,690	\$6,228,186,980
-2	\$4,667,938,261	\$7,923,005,678
-1	\$6,565,336,590	\$9,787,306,246
0	\$8,652,474,751	\$11,838,036,870
1	\$10,948,326,728	\$14,093,840,557
2	\$11,866,763,903	\$14,968,224,613
3	\$12,009,044,795	\$15,062,047,074
4	\$10,507,553,777	\$13,507,251,781
5	\$9,738,913,657	\$12,679,976,960
6	\$9,049,409,524	\$11,925,974,656
7	\$8,793,954,979	\$11,599,572,121
...
24	\$8,435,350,477	\$8,435,350,477

Chart 2: NPV Profile of Operating Income from KSM Mine Plan

NPV Profile for KSM Project at 10% Discount Rate
(Different Time Horizons)

The KSM mine starts production at year 0, and the NPV profile reaches the maximum soon after, which is an example of a “rising” NPV Profile. The NPV ranges from \$7 billion to \$11 billion based on operating cash flow. For comparison, the net present value of the total GDP impacts from the single project KSM ranges between \$40 billion and \$60 billion. Net present value of total GDP represents the discounted value of the total GDP impacts from capital costs and revenues.

Canada's national total metals mining GDP is around \$15 billion per year, as in Table 1.12. The KSM project has an average GDP impact of \$4.7 billion per year over the entire 13-year timeline, compared with \$7.9 billion per year after the mine is in production. After the mine is in production, it pays an average of \$485 million in taxes per year, according to Seabridge Gold Corp. (2022) and indirect taxes \$794 million per year, according to my calculations.

All the results here consider only mineral production. It is also possible to consider minerals processing in Canada, as this is an essential part of the supply chain built on the value of primary minerals.

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